

ADDRESS DAHYAKOTA

Abdullayev Zohidjon Tolibjon O'g'li

Namangan State University, 3rd year student of History

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7528136>

Annotatsiya:

Ushbu maqolada Namangan viloyati Uychi tumani Jiydakapa qishlog'ida joylashgan qadimiy Daxyaota manzilgohi qurilish uslubi, olib borilgan arxeologik izlanishlar natijasi, manzilgoh tarixiy ahamiyati va boshqalar haqida ma'lumotlar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Daxyaota (Dakhyakota), Jiydakapa, Ovchi buva, A. Anorboev, A. Dakimov, Axsikent, Norin daryo.

Аннотация:

В данной статье представлены сведения о стиле застройки древнего городища Дахьяота, расположенного в селе Джийдакапа Уйчинского района Наманганской области, результаты археологических исследований, историческое значение городища и др.

Ключевые слова: Дахьяота (Дахьякота), Жийдакапа, Овчи Бува, А. Анорбоев, А. Дакимов, Ахсикент, Норин река.

Annotation:

This article provides information about the construction style of the ancient Dakhyaota settlement located in the village of Jiydakapa, Uychi district, Namangan region, the results of archaeological research, the historical significance of the settlement, etc.

Key words: Dakhyaota (Dakhyakota), Jiydakapa, Ovchi buva, A. Anorboev, A. Dakimov, Ahsikent, Norin Daryo.

Dakhyaota (Dakhyak ota) is a village in Uychi district. 17 kilometers from the district center. The nearest railway station (Namangan) is 10 kilometers away. Jiydakapa village borders Kurama villages of Namangan district. Dakhyaota - Dakhiyak means eleven fathers. At this time, he means Dakhyaota - a person who has disappeared and is actually alive. There are legends that Dakhyaota is the youngest of 11 siblings. The elders are Grandfather Ovchi buva (Unhayat), Grandfather Grandfather and Grandfather King (in Aksu district of Kyrgyzstan), Grandfather Kuk night, Grandfather Mashhad (Unhayat) and others. There is another story related to Dakyaota. The Norin River flows from a place near Ovchi Buva. Brothers and sisters prayed in the presence of grandmother Ovchi. One day, due to a flood, Dakhyaota is late for prayer. The congregation prayed and asked God to let the river flow a little further. After that, the river begins to flow further and gets the name "Norin". That is why they say that there will be no floods in Dakhyaota. The population is 2518 people (2010). He is engaged in cotton farming, cattle breeding, rice farming, and horticulture.¹

In the village of Dakhyakota, there is also a shrine of Dakhyakota, and the name of the village is related to the name of this breed. The old people of this village say that in the center of the

¹ Abdulla Jabbor Namangan Region (compact data collection) "Namangan" village - 2011. b-80

old cemetery there was an old mosque and a shrine. So there is no doubt that these findings are one of the more than 70 different cities and towns in the Fergana Valley mentioned by historians in the 9th-12th centuries. The reason for this is that he lived near the water near the Norin River and Chortoksoy. The population was engaged in agriculture and production. Similar baths were also found in Ahsikent, but the technology of its operation was different. The presence of the underground Gungalak bath belonging to the 10th-12th centuries in the city of Kosonsoy, which is still operating today, can be understood to what extent the level of knowledge and culture of our descendants in the Fergana Valley was high. In order to maintain the moderation of the bathhouse, that is, not to waste heat, the architect of that time built it underground and heated it with a little heat.² Recently, the authors found the remains of the foundation of an ancient building in the yard of A. Dakimov, a resident of Dakhyakota village, Jiydakapa village, Uychi district, Namangan region. It was determined that this structure belongs to approximately the 9th-11th centuries. Archaeologists A. Anorboev, B. Ruzinov and Sh. Nasriddinov, Yu. Ismoilov carried out scientific research here. According to the preliminary results, it was found that the remains of this structure are actually the remains of a bath belonging to the 9th-11th centuries. As a result, three rooms of the bath, which have been preserved today, were opened and studied. We know that in the Islamic world madrasahs for students were built only in large centralized cities in order to further develop science, trade and production. In addition, around the Madrasa there was a complex consisting of a mosque, a bathhouse and stalls of artisans. This is a proof that our ancestors thoroughly mastered religious and secular sciences in the Middle Ages, especially geometry, mathematics, chemistry, medicine, and architecture to the level of art. Coins minted during the Samoni and Karakhanid period were also found in this place. Another important find is the remains of foundations and walls made with rarely used 37 x 37 x 4 cm baked bricks and 30 x 14 x 4 cm brick samples. There were also found here mysterious pottery vessels made in different styles, fragments of crucibles, glass shards, ceramic pipe fragments, remains of copper articles and their fragments. The bricks were beaten with a specially prepared clay mixture.³ The scientists of the Samarkand Institute of Archeology named after Yakhyo Gulomov of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan opened archaeological excavations in the territory of the shrine. As a result, it was proved that this settlement was one of the 70 cities in the Fargona valley with the development of science, culture and crafts of the 9th-11th centuries. In a word, Dahyakota village, like the ancient city of Namangan, is waiting for us to find out that its original age is more than 1000 years. Preservation and study of such settlements is not only the work of representatives of the field, but also the duty and responsibility of all our citizens who are interested in their history. President I.A. As Karimov rightly noted, "Of course, the spirituality of any people or nation cannot be imagined without its history, unique customs and traditions, and life values. In this regard, spiritual heritage, cultural assets, old historical monuments serve as one of the most important factors."⁴

² <https://n.ziyouz.com/portal-haqida/xarita/maqolalar/daxyakotaning-ko-hna-hammomi>

³ Rozinov B., Rajabova S., Usmailov Y., Kasimov A. Cultural heritage of Namangan region. Namangan - 2013. - B-28

⁴ Karimov I. High spirituality is an inexhaustible power. - Tashkent: Spirituality, 2008. - B. 29-30.

References:

1. Abdulla Jabbar Namangan Region (compact data collection) "Namangan" parish - 2011. B-287
2. <https://n.ziyouz.com/portal-haqida/xarita/maqolalar/dakhyakotaning-ko-hna-hammomi>
3. Rozinov B., Rajabova S., Usmailov Y., Kasimov A Cultural heritage of Namangan region. Namangan - 2013. B-115
4. Karimov I. High spirituality is an inexhaustible power. - Tashkent: Spirituality, 2008 B-108

